

FROM FOOD INDUSTRY TO FERMENTATION

VISS
INFO PACK
N.01

From food industry residues to bio-based packaging, the ViSS approach connects feedstock conditioning, fermentation and optimisation, green solvent extraction, and final material transformation into a circular solution.

Discover part of the value chain in this info pack.

THE VISS VALUE CHAIN: FIRST STEPS

Poly(3-hydroxybutyrate-co-3-hydroxyvalerate) (PHBV) is a fully biodegradable and biocompatible copolymer belonging to the polyhydroxyalkanoate (PHA) family. **Within the ViSS project**, PHBV is produced using industrial organic residues – sugar-rich effluents and poultry by-products – providing a sustainable, circular alternative to fossil-based plastics for food packaging.

DESCRIPTION OF THE PROCESS

TECHNICAL POINTS

- Green solvent substitution**
1,3-dioxolane enables efficient, non-toxic PHBV extraction, offering a sustainable alternative to chloroform.
- Residue valorisation**
Industrial by-products provide effective nutrient sources for PHBV synthesis, reducing dependency on commercial feedstocks.
- Metabolic control of polymer composition**
Controlled precursor addition (propionic/valeric acids) allows fine-tuning of 3HV content for tailored material properties.
- Process integration and circularity**
Reuse of fermentation media and nutrient streams enhances resource efficiency and supports the circular bioeconomy model.

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